

NEXT GENERATION TRANSVAGINAL MESH: BIOMIMETIC MATERIALS AND EVOLVING SURGICAL TECHNIQUES FOR PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE

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ABSTRACT

Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) widely prevalent pelvic disorder affecting up to 65% of women over 40years of age, significantly affecting quality of life, sexual function, & urinary health. Native tissue repair was historically regarded as the primary surgical strategy, due to significant recurrence rates, transvaginal mesh was introduced to enhance anatomical durability & provide better apical support. Although structural outcomes improved, mounting reports of mesh-related complications were observed mesh-related complications including erosion, chronic pelvic pain, dyspareunia, infection & de novo urinary dysfunction. This led to major regulatory actions between 2008 & 2019, resulting in restrictions on transvaginal mesh use in many regions. As a result, focus shift toward biomaterial advancements & precision-driven surgical methods. Modern mesh technologies focus on enhanced biocompatibility, optimized pore structure, & Balanced

mechanical properties. Recent developments involve refining (or) replacing conventional polypropylene constructs with advanced materials such as polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), tetanized polypropylene and biodegradable polymers like (PCL) polycaprolactone. Novel bioengineering approaches, including auxetic geometries, 3D melt electro-writing fabrication, antibiotic-loaded scaffolds, and patient-specific implants are designed to mimic native tissue biomechanics while reducing inflammation and long-term complications. Current approaches in surgical management prioritize minimally invasive, function-preserving techniques,

including robotic-assisted sacrocolpopexy, bilateral utero sacral ligament reconstruction, uterus-sparing hysteropexy and anchorless stabilization systems. Overall, these innovations are guiding a transition toward biomimetic, safety-centered/oriented, & individualized pelvic floor construction, redefining pop management through the integration of materials science, precise surgical techniques, and patient-reported outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Pelvicorganprolapse; Transvaginalmesh; Biomaterials; Polyvinylidene fluoride(PVDF); Polypropylene mesh; Biodegradable scaffolds; Auxetic design; 3D melt electro writing; Sacrocolpopexy; Robotic-assisted surgery; Uterus-sparing procedures; Pelvic floor reconstruction.

INTRODUCTION

Pelvic organ prolapse is the commonest condition in which the pelvic organs drop down and stick out into or beyond the vaginal canal, causing distress and symptoms such as a feeling of heaviness in the pelvis, vaginal bulge, and sexual dysfunction. Figure 1 shows illustration of the incremental descent of the uterus. It affects the quality of life of women over 40, with prevalence estimates reaching up to 65% when physical examinations and symptoms are combined. Risk factors include vaginal delivery, aging, obesity, and chronic pressure in the abdomen.^[1] Surgical treatment continues the initial therapy for symptomatic POP, with native tissue repair being the most frequently undertaken procedure. Although recurrence rates following conventional repair remain a challenge. To enhance anatomical outcomes, transvaginal mesh was initiated; Its use has been associated with mesh-related complications, leading to regulatory requirements, and it continues to be debated in terms of safety. With the evolving evidence, there's a need to analyze the current literature on mesh. This review aims to summarize the indications, outcomes, and evolving techniques associated with transvaginal mesh in the treatment of POP.

Figure 1: Showing the stages of prolapse, it illustrates the progression of the uterus.

What is the purpose of the new design's evolution?

For a better approach (or) to identify the obstacle in existing treatment (or) to improve patient Safety and fresh design concepts were proposed. Usage of old meshes (traditional synthetic mesh) causing some consequences such a new auxetic mesh design that is strong enough, flexible enough, similar to body tissue, and bearing a load.

Which design is better?

During printing, the material overlap occurs with maximum load (-7N) capacity in re-entrant Evans compared to natural vaginal tissue. Due to its stronger characteristic, its stiffness restricts the use of pop repair. While the Lozenge grid (-35N) shows that a stable mechanical performance. suggest that it is suitable for all kinds of situations of moderate loads. The natural tissues of the vagina, which is very closely matured to the square grid & three-star honeycomb design. Which illustrate the same kind of elastic phenomena with minimal load. For more improvement in the elastic nature of mesh, further researchers will concentrate on better printing settings (they might carry out in vivo tests).^[2]

Invented meshes that recreate the physiological structural change of natural vaginal tissue. While maintaining the mechanical compatibility with tissue for better therapeutical outcomes in healing of pop.

Due to the stressful environment of the wall of the vagina and in vivo loading configurations, which are completely unknown. It is very tough to achieve the stiffness goal. There is a chance of significant fluctuations occurring in testing procedures (uniaxial versus biaxial), the tissue state (healthy vs. prolapsed), and experimental settings (in vivo, in vitro, ex vivo, animal, or cadaver research). Based on certain maximized results, the pop meshes' stiffness is predicted.^[3] Standardized physiological settings, which are very crucial for making the design of pop mesh, and they are clinically suitable.

Types of Meshes and Grafts

Materials used for prolapse repair can be broadly divided into three categories depending on their source and how they interact with the body.

1. Synthetic Non-Absorbable Meshes: This group consists of permanent materials that remain in the body to provide long-term structural reinforcement. Among these, **Polypropylene (pp)** is most frequently selected because it offers high tensile strength at a

relatively low cost.^[1,2] **Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)** is considered a more stable and biocompatible substitute.^[5] **Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)**, including ORIHME variant used in Japan, tends to produce less tissue reaction but may have a greater tendency to displace.⁶ **Polyurethane (PU)**, due to its flexibility, more closely replicates the elasticity of natural tissue. (Table1)

Table 1: Represent the material types along with Merits and Demerits.

Material	Type	Merits	Demerits
Polypropylene	Synthetic	Strong, Cheap, high durability. ⁴	Stiff brittle, high erosion risk ⁴ .
PVDF	Synthetic	More resistant to degradation than PP ^{7,8}	Stiff compared to PU ⁸ .
PTFE	Synthetic	Biological inert with minimal tissue reaction and low infection adherence due to its smooth micro porous structure ⁹ .	Limited tissue ingrowth leading to higher risk of displacement and difficult integration with surrounding tissue ⁹ .
Polyurethane (PU)	Synthetic	High elasticity matches native tissue ⁸ .	Concerns regarding long-term durability.

2. Biological Grafts: Unlike synthetic meshes, biological grafts originated from living tissues. When the patients's own tissue-such as the round-ligament is used and that eliminates the risk of infection.^[1,10] It is termed an autologous graft. Grafts obtained from human donors are called allografts, whereas those derived from animal sourced like porcine or bovine tissue are referred to as xenografts.^[4]

3. Advanced or Next-Generation Materials: Recent innovations focus on biodegradable polymers such as **Polycaprolactone (PCL)** and **Poly(lactic acid) (PLA)**.^[11] These materials serve as temporary frameworks that gradually degrade as the body restores its native support structures. Additionally, emerging graphene-based nano composites like Hastalexare under investigation for their superior mechanical strength combined with enhanced elasticity.

Evolution of Prolapse Management

The approach to pelvic organ prolapse repair has evolved through four major stages.

Native Tissue Repair: Initially, surgeons depended entirely on repairing the patient's own supportive ligaments.

However, recurrence rates approaching 30% highlighted the need for additional reinforcement methods.^[7,12] **Transvaginal Mesh Expansion(Early 2000s):** Synthetic

meshes, originally designed for hernia repairs, were introduced into vaginal surgeries to achieve more durable anatomical correction.^[4,7]

Regulatory Challenges (2008-2019): Increasing reports of complications-such as mesh erosion and persistent pelvic pain- prompted regulatory authorities, including the FDA, to categorize transvaginal mesh devices as high risk, eventually restricting their use.^[7]

Contemporary Precision Approaches: Current practice favors sacrocolpopexy, where the vaginal vault is attached to the sacrum for long-term stability.^[13,14] Ongoing research now emphasizes patient-specific solutions, including 3D-printed meshes and auxetic structures engineered to better mimic human tissue mechanics.^[8,11]

Mechanism of Action

Pelvic floor meshes function through a combination of structural support and biological interaction with surrounding tissues.

Mechanical Reinforcement

Immediately after implantation, the mesh acts as a supportive framework that stabilizes the pelvic organs. By compensating for weakened or damaged ligaments, it restores anatomical positioning and provides necessary strength.^[4,15]

Biological incorporation

Following placement, the body initiates a localized immune response. Macrophages and other immune cells migrate into the mesh pores, initiating a regulated inflammatory process. This response promotes fibroblast activity and collagen deposition, resulting in fibrous tissue formation around and within the mesh. Over time, this process integrates the implant into the host tissue, anchoring it securely.^[1,14]

Key Design Considerations

Pore Dimensions

Adequate pore size-generally greater than 1mm-is essential to permit immune cell migration and effective infection control. Smaller pores may restrict cellular entry while allowing bacterial colonization, thereby increasing infection risk.^[6]

Properties of textile and pore size

Small Pores (<1mm): When scar tissue encapsulates the filaments, fibrotic bridging progression occurs that eventually leads to contraction and stiffness of the tissue.^[8,14]

Large Pores (>1mm): Allows the macrophages into the tissue via blood vessel by penetration that minimize the risk of infection and protecting elasticity (Figure 2)^[7,8]

Figure 2: Demonstrates the variation between structures of small and large pores.

Stress Distribution

Excessively rigid meshes may bear the entire mechanical load, reducing physiological stress on adjacent muscles. This can lead to muscle weakening and disuse atrophy over time.^[3,4]

Auxetic Structural Patterns

Advanced mesh configurations incorporate auxetic geometry, characterized by lateral expansion upon stretching. This design minimizes folding or bunching under tension and helps reduce mechanical irritation to surrounding tissues.^[2]

Initially native tissue restoration was implemented for pelvic organ prolapse, as these are regarded as minimal risk and acceptable, as it offers the benefits of a transvaginal approach later for better anatomical support. TVM was introduced. It shows increased success rates.^[7]

Although^[1] in 2006 the FDA raised a first warning in response to over 1000 complications reported. In 2016, the FDA recategorized surgical mesh for POP as high risk. By 2019 the FDA ordered the marketing of TV repair to be stopped because of reports of mesh-related complications in the US and several European countries (Table 2).

Table 2: Regulatory events and Time line of mesh safety.

Year	Regulatory Body	Action
2005	FDA	Transvaginal mesh was first introduced in the US for POP surgical management. ^[7]
2008	FDA	The first safety notification was issued concerning the use of Transvaginal mesh and its associated severe complications. ^[16]
2011	FDA	Updated Safety Report Stated that complications were not rare. ^[16]
2016	FDA	Categorized of POP mesh as class IV (high risk) medical devices. ^[7]
2019	FDA/NICE	Withdrawl of Transvaginal mesh kits for descent of the anterior compartments. ^[7]
2023	EUGA	The position statement advocates Native tissue repair(NTR) as primary surgical option for POP ^[13]

Surgical Mesh Retrieval due to discomfort and following long term complications

In a survey, 3.3% of 2 patients had de novo SUI after 1 year of follow-up, 3 patients of 61%, and 2 patients of 4.8% were diagnosed with UII after 2-3years of follow-up. In POP surgery, the mid-urethral sling operation is also carried out to reduce the need for a second operation or to reduce the development of SUI afterprolapse; for thatreason, both surgeries can be done at the same time. 6.7% of the de novo UII rate has been noted, which can be explained by the mid-urethral surgery. 3.3% of dyspareunia cases were noted because of low levels of sexual engagement. It is important to know that after 1year of surgery, only 5 patients are sexually engaged. An interesting point is that the patient activity of participating in sexual intercourse might have had the risk of mesh exposure, but they did not experience any mesh exposure. The follow-up report by NICE of a surgery done in the UK shows 12% of patients undergoing pelvic PP mesh repair experience from extrusion. If the follow-up exceeds 3.5 years, the percentage would be changed due to the high risk of mesh extrusion and exposure. But there is a major problem in which the patient may feel vaginal bleeding, irregular discharge, dyspareunia, and discomfort.^[4]

When the mesh is eaten away slowly by a chemical reaction, it has to be removed from the PP mesh implant. To preventfurther damage to the surrounding vaginal tissue. It is considered the next essential care. However, typically the mesh had already gotten blended with the surrounding vaginal wall. It is difficult toremove it, so it requires complex steps to performthe procedure. Surgeons who are going to performthe surgery must be acquires of knowledge and skills. They should explain the procedure along with the possibility of the

occurrence of long-term damage. Even with the removal of the mesh, there is a chance of recurring pop symptoms in 20% of patients with new challenges compared to primary treatment. The pop mesh may be removed completely or in part in a surgery.^[17] To reduce the risk of post-operative vaginal stenosis, experts only perform the procedure. Some of the other conservative methods for the treatment include the use of estrogen, antiseptics, and antibiotics (to reduce infection). Another important segment in the usage of POP meshes: long-term use of POP meshes can cause de novo SUI, UII, and dyspareunia.

Modern Surgical Kits

Third-generation surgical kits are designed to be lightweight, with larger or wider pores. Dimensions better secured in place (fixation), these modifications were introduced to address and minimize the complication rates and risks that were common with older mesh designs or systems.^[7]

6-point fixation systems

6-point fixation systems have been introduced to maintain the support you benefit from with mesh while reducing excessive tension or limiting tension (Figure 3). To encourage better immune cell movements (macrophages) and reduce infection risk, the kit makes use of an ultra-lightweight mesh (21g/m²). Designed with a combination of small pores, or micropores (100-150/μm), and large coarse or macropores (1.9-2.8mm).^[7]

Figure 3 illustrate the differences between first generation mesh and modern mesh implants.

Titanized mesh kits

Clinical data indicate that the Tillop PROA system, made with titanized polypropylene, provides effective apical support, achieving success rates of 82 percent while also improving patients' overall quality of life.^[7]

Single incision and sacrospinous Fixation kits

Objective cure rates of 78.6% and 91.7 percent have been reported with the elevated system, a single-incision kit intended for anterior and/or apical repair and secured to the sacrospinous ligament. This system reduces mesh surface area and eliminated the requirement for trocars.^[7]

Polyvinylidene Fluoride (PVDF) Tapes

To enable bilateral reconstruction of the uterosacral ligaments, the DYNA mesh-CESA kit employs tapes manufactured in defined dimensions (8.8cm/length).^[5] Unlike traditional polypropylene, it utilizes PVDF, a material known for enhanced stability and tissue compatibility (Figure 4).^[5]

Figure 4 Structure of PVDF sutured at the cervix which is covered by the peritoneum. The mesh arms follows the ligament of uterosacral to avoid obstruction.

Anchorless and Self-Retaining Systems

At 2-year follow-up, stage prolapse resolution was observed in 84.2% of patients treated with the Lyra (self-retaining support) system. This technology replicates the function of the pubocervical fascia while eliminating the need for complex anchoring technique.^[7]

Japanese PTFE Kits

Because of its lower friction coefficient (PTFE), polytetrafluoroethylene radiopaque material may predispose the mesh to slippage unless mechanical fixation is applied.^[6] In Japan, kits such as ORIHIME incorporate this radio plaque material, which can be clearly visualized on 3DCT imaging; compared to polypropylene, it produced a milder inflammatory response.

Advanced/New Generation Transvaginal System

It includes the Calistar kit system, which has demonstrated high anatomical Success reaching 96%, along with Notable Improvement in Urinary Symptoms and patients' Reported Quality of Life.

Recent advancements in surgical techniques

Contemporary/recent technical advancement or directed toward enhancing procedural precision, restricting synthetic material usage when appropriate, and advancing biomimetic fabrication methods.^[13]

Minimally invasive robotic-assisted sacrocolpopexy (RSC)

Robotic platforms or systems, including the da Vinci Xi and Hinotari¹⁸, provide surgeons with superior 3D visualization and precise control within the deep pelvic cavity. As a result, RSC has gained popularity, enabling complex suturing while reducing surgeon fatigue and decreasing conversion to open procedure (1.33%) relative to laparoscopy (7.14%).^[7]

Bilateral cervicosacropexy or dual-sided cervicosacropexy

Unlike conventional sacrocolpopexy, which relies on unilateral tension, this technique achieves bilateral replacement of the uterosacral ligaments, offering precise apical support. A specialized semicircular hook guides retroperitoneal mesh placement along the peritoneal folds, minimizing vascular and neural complications.^[5]

Autologous Round Ligaments (ARL) grafts

To provide mesh-free apical support, a robotic approach harvested the patients round ligaments during hysterectomy.^[10] Reinforced end-to-end into a 7 to 9 cm graft, the ligaments offered safe and effective support, eliminating the risk of mesh-related complications.^[10]

Ventral mesh rectopexy (VMR) variation

In managing posterior compartment prolapse, ventral mesh rectopexy has been adapted to skip rectal fixation.^[18] This approach preserves functional improvement, eases obstructed defecation, and minimizes the risk of rectal erosion.^[18]

3D melt electrowriting (MEW)

Recent innovation in bioengineering makes it possible to produce tailored biodegradable scaffolds.^[11] Adjusting printing parameters like voltage and speed allows for the creation of auxetic geometries (four designs Figure 5₂), which expand laterally when stretched, mirroring the hyperelastic behaviour of native vaginal tissue and is checked by uniaxial tensile test.(figure 6)

Figure 5: Four different types of auxetic designs.^[2]

Figure 6: Uniaxial tensile test on native vaginal tissue samples.^[2]

Uterus-sparing hysteropexy

A strong shift toward uterus-conserving (or sparing) procedures has emerged in clinical practice demonstrating effectiveness equal to concomitant hysterectomy.^[14,19] preserving the uterus has been associated with lower intraoperative blood loss, shorter hospital stays, and a decreased risk of mesh exposure.

Antibiotic-loaded biodegradable implant

Innovations in pelvic floor repair include 3D-printed PCL meshes coated with antibiotic like ciprofloxacin⁷. Laboratory testing indicates that such coatings can reduce bacterial biofilm formation by 99%⁷, mitigating the infection risks often. Observed with standard pelvic implants.^[20]

CONCLUSION

The dramatic changes occur in the treatment of pelvic organ prolapse, departing from native tissue healing to man-made structural support and now biometric-guided treatment. The relevance of patient safety, material compatibility, and longterm evaluation was highlight by some difficulties and regulatory boundaries, inspite the fact, transvaginal mesh systems which improve morphological restoration. Upcoming techniques and procedures concentrate on reducing the pathological inflammation and improving pore configuration, risk of infection, integration of tissueand pressure allocation. The de novo innovations treatment includes PVDFbased tapes, auxetic mesh, biodegradable scaffolds coated with antibiotics, robotic-assisted sacrocolpopexy, and uterus sparing. These examples show an intervention of functional recovery protocols. For quality of life and long-term clinical follow-up, it would be given in further future studies. The final end, which describes the pop mesh safety, long casting, and patient-centered pelvic floor repair by medicating between biological hormones and mechanical reinforcement.

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